

Pupils' Cognitive and Affective Reading Profiles in Relation to Age, Sex and Family Economic Status

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Abstract:- Past reading experience, attitudes towards reading, reading self-efficacy, use of strategy, and reading habits are some of the factors that may influence reading achievement among elementary school pupils. In this study, these factors collectively termed as cognitive and affective reading profile are explored as to their relationship with the pupils' age, sex, and family economic status. A total of 205 Grade 6 pupils from a school district in Mandaon, Masbate selected using systematic sampling comprised the respondents of the study. Chi-square statistic was used to analyze the data. The findings show that the pupils have a poor reading habits and low self – efficacy, undecided to the value of library, reading difficult texts and of the graphics. Based from the findings of the study, the researcher drew the following conclusions that the low weighted mean obtained on the factor; reading and self-efficacy and reading habits are a contributing factors on the low reading proficiency level of the pupils. Past experiences with reading, attitudes towards reading and reading strategies are also a great contributor to the reading experiences of the pupil. Age and gender do not have a significant relation to reading but they also dictate on what appropriate tasks to be given along reading activity. Family income does affect the readability of the child, but parental involvement can be of great significance to build readership among children. Economic status need to be explored more whether it is really a cause of differences in reading achievement.

Keywords:- Reading profiles, reading factors, reading instruction, reading intervention program

I. INTRODUCTION

Reading is considered as one of the fundamental skills that is crucial for individuals to be successful in their journey towards excellence. This is also one of the macro skills that should be developed among students. Aside from this, it is also considered as the foundation for all academic learning. Learning to read, as well as learning to write and count, is crucial to a child's success in school and in later life., teaching and developing reading skill is not an easy undertaking for there are barriers that hinder in learning and developing this skill. Ideally speaking, it is expected that high school students are already readers and should have developed reading comprehension as well. Yet, it is quite alarming to note that during reading assessments, there are still students who are assessed to be slow readers and even non-readers.

Several schools provide different interventions in different subject areas to help students to cope with the essential skills needed in a particular field of discipline. Department of Education, in support of the program "No Child Left Behind Policy", provides different interventions to reach and educate every child in the Philippines through traditional and alternative learning systems. These interventions are well-planned and carried out by the teachers. Academic interventions are embedded in the school curricula with a primary purpose to help the students in their academic struggles. In addition, they are conducting remedial classes during summer to tutor or coach the learners with learning gaps or subject area deficiency as stated in DepEd Order No.13, s.2018. Additionally, according to the Department of Education Order No. 29, s. 2015, students who had failed no more than a pair of courses before the date of implementation of DO 8, s. 2015 might get promoted to the subsequent grade level; however, learning opportunities to catch up on or progress on the specific abilities of the topics they failed should be provided available for the academic year (SY) 2015-2016. In addition, the Department of Education supports ECARP (Every Child A Reader Program), a nationwide campaign aimed at helping every Filipino child be a reader at his or her level. It is meant to give pupils in elementary schools the reading and writing techniques required to become young, independent readers and writers. Additionally, it offers educators an entire academic year of training to assist them in becoming fluent and self-sufficient problem solvers.

As cited by Akyol, Çakiroğlu and Kuruyer (2014) research has proven that enrichment reading programs are one of the applications positively affecting reading, reading comprehension, reading awareness and expression skills (Goodman, 2007; Schreiber, 2003). Meanwhile, Alexander, Carr and Schwaneflugel (1995) give important information about students with reading difficulties and also point out the efficiency of enrichment reading programs in the elimination of reading difficulties. Consequently, if applied in the learning process, specifically along reading programs in the classroom setting, enhancement of reading proficiency of the students can easily be attained.

Though there are several reading programs which primarily aimed to increase learners' readership, still there are individuals classified as frustrated reader and non-reader. The researcher believes that the outcome of this study will serve as one of the bases for a proposed reading program as a remedial measure to improve pupils' performance when it comes to reading which will result to an improved performance of the learners. This will also help the teachers and school heads in planning, formulating and adopting policies to remediate the pupils' reading problems.

A. Body of paper

Pupils’ cognitive and affective reading profiles in relation to age, sex, and family economic status was conceptualized to help teachers in teaching reading which is considered as one of the crucial skills needed for survival in the world and this will be useful for them in identifying the needs of the pupils in a reading activity. Also, the result of this can also help them innovate and develop right interventions along reading. To students, as the center of the curriculum, this study will help them to cope with their problem in reading. The result of the study will also benefit the administrators and the curriculum implementers to further innovate the existing reading program that would enhance the reading skill of the students and to answer the existing problem of both the teachers and the students with regards to reading. This study sought to answer the following questions: (1) What are the cognitive and affective reading profile of the Grade – 6 pupils of Mandaon North District along: (a) Past Experiences in Reading; (b) Attitudes towards Reading; (c) Reading and Self – Efficacy; (d) Reading Strategies; and (e) Reading Habits? and (2) Is there a relationship between the profile and reading background factors of Grade – 6 pupils of Mandaon North District? The main focus of this study is to determine the reading profile of the Grade 6 pupils of public elementary schools of Mandaon North District school year 2019-2020. The aspects being looked into are the extent of influence of the background factors that affects the reading skills of the pupils and their demographic profile.

II. METHODS

A. Sample and Sampling Procedure

The respondents of this study were the Grade 6 pupils of public elementary schools of Mandaon North District. Using the Slovin’s formula, there were 205 pupils identified as the respondents of the study. From the identified respondents, nine (9) of these total population were from Mabato-bato Elementary Schools, twenty-four (24) were from Diogenes R. Cabarles Elementary School, sixty-nine (69) were from Cabitan Central School, twenty-one (21) were from Dayao Elementary School, twenty-six (26) were from Alas

Elementary School, thirty-two (32) were from Tagpu Elementary School, eight (8) were from Tabuk Elementary School and sixteen (16) were from San Juan Elementary School. The systematic sampling method was employed in this study. With this method, the researcher was able to facilitate and identify the respondents of the study by identifying a fixed starting point and the constant interval.

B. Research Instrument

To determine the cognitive and affective reading profiles of the pupils, an instrument from the study of Boakye (2017), “Exploring Students’ Reading Profiles to Guide a Reading Intervention Programme” was used.

C. Statistical Tool

The Chi-square statistic was used for testing relationships between categorical variables. The demographic profile and the reading background factors were statistically analyzed if there are any significant relationships among them.

D. Design

This study made of the correlational design to answer the research questions. Social reading profile such as age, sex, and family economic status were correlated with cognitive and affective reading profiles. Data were gathered in the months of November 2019 to January 2020 during school year 2019-2020. The gathered data were then analyzed using chi-square statistics to find out relationships.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Cognitive and Affective Reading Profile

➤ *Reading Profile in Terms of Past Reading Experiences*

In terms of past experiences with reading, most of the respondents strongly agreed on the factor “Before I could read for myself, my family members used to read to me” with 4.36 weighted mean. On the other hand, some of the respondents were undecided on the factor “I often visited the library to read or to borrow books to read at home” with a weighted mean of 3.20.

Table 1: Reading profile in terms of past reading experiences

Item	Weighted Mean	Description
PAST READING EXPERIENCES		
1. I read books for pleasure during my childhood.	4.10	Agree
2. I started reading between the ages of 4-6.	4.05	Agree
3. Before I could read for myself members of my family used to read to me.	4.36	Strongly Agree
4. I started reading in my mother tongue as a child.	3.85	Agree
5. My mother used to encourage me to read a lot of books.	3.83	Agree
6. I often visited the library to read or to borrow books to read at home.	3.20	Undecided
7. There have always been books in my family’s home.	4.35	Strongly Agree
8. My teachers emphasized reading for pleasure.	4.14	Agree
Average Weighted Mean	3.98	Agree

Based on the result of the study, it was found out that most of the Grade VI pupils of Mandaon North District elementary schools had experienced reading with their family members. Most researches have proven the effectiveness of the parents' reading to their children. According to Cullinan and Bagert (1996), children become readers when their parents read to them. A family reading time also shows that when parents and family members like to read this will help the child develop their love for reading. As to Heavenridge (2015), families that read together succeed together. The most significant measure of a child's achievement in early literacy and future academic achievement is involvement by parents. Additionally, he mentioned findings of the American Academy of Pediatrics that illustrate how reading out to young children daily, from infancy, fosters early developmental milestones and helps in the development of vital language, literacy, and social skills. Akindele (2012) said that parents should begin reading with their youngsters right away as they are able to understand sound and that it is ideal for children to be exposed to books as well as reading at an early age. The fact that it has an important beneficial effect on children's reading skills later in life (Kalb & Ours, 2012) and that the volume of parent-child book reading interactions predicts children's afterward receptive vocabulary, reading comprehension, and internal drive to read (Lira et al. 2018), the parents must be motivated to read alongside and with their children from an early age, at age 4-5 every day. Moreover, early reading with the kids helps them learn to speak, interact, bond with their family members, and read early themselves. The more reading kids do, the more quickly they will develop as readers.

However, the result also revealed that the respondents were undecided about going to the library to borrow books to read at home. Accordingly, there is an insufficient supply

of reading materials available in the school library, and in some cases, most of the elementary schools in Mandaon North District where the respondents came from having no library at all. Relevant to this result, it was mentioned in the study of Oyewo (2012) that because of limited resources in the library, it has a negative impact on the attitude of the pupils towards the use of the school library. Moreover, pupils only go to the library to do their assignments but not for reading. On the contrary, several studies proven the positive implications of the library's operation in the reading performance of the learners for it serves an invaluable role in the educational set-up, and most people especially students use the library for their work (Itsekor&Nwokeoma, 2017). According to Busayo (2011), libraries offer resources for an array of reading preferences at various points of one's intellectual growth as well as for enjoyment. The results of the study by Lonsdale (2003) showed that effective library programs that are well-staffed, funded, and supported could result in higher achievement among students. Furthermore, it was found that school libraries have a positive effect on student literacy and educational achievements based on the study conducted by the National Library of New Zealand. Additionally, it results in favorable attitudes toward learning, such as greater motivation, an improved attitude toward academic activities, increased self-esteem, more reading for pleasure, and effective curricula or educational results (Anyagbu et al., 2016). Additionally, it has an advantageous effect on children's performance in school and academic development (Chukwueke, 2018). Likewise, it was highlighted that school libraries have an integral part in helping children attain high exam scores. In order to encourage children to read more, the school curriculum should provide time for accessing the library, and its collections ought to include a wide range of reading material (Itsekor&Nwokeoma, 2017).

B. Reading Profile in Terms of Attitudes towards Reading

Table 2: Reading profile in terms of attitudes towards reading

Item	Weighted Mean	Description
ATTITUDES TOWARDS READING		
1. I have always believed that reading was a good thing to do.	4.60	Strongly Agree
2. I have favorite subjects that I read about.	4.54	Strongly Agree
3. I enjoy reading when I know the subject matter.	4.37	Strongly Agree
4. Reading well will help me with my studies.	4.57	Strongly Agree
5. I enjoy reading difficult texts.	2.92	Undecided
6. I feel there is too much to read in the English subject.	3.28	Undecided
7. I find academic articles difficult to read.	3.37	Undecided
8. Reading helps me understand difficult concepts.	4.37	Strongly Agree
9. If the assignment project is interesting, I can read difficult material.	3.56	Agree
10. If my teacher discusses something interesting, I will read more about it.	3.82	Agree
Average Weighted Mean	3.94	Agree

As to the attitude towards reading of the pupil-respondents, it was revealed that most of them strongly agreed with the factors "I have always believed that reading was a good thing to do" with a weighted mean of 4.60. On the other hand, the respondents were undecided in the factor "I enjoy reading difficult texts" with 2.92 weighted mean.

According to the study's findings, the majority of participants value reading. The majority of them think reading is beneficial and can aid them in their studies. According to research by Avalone (2005), children who have good attitudes toward reading are more probable to enjoy reading, be willing to devote time to reading, and be successful readers for the duration of their existence. As

mentioned by Nyarko, et. al. (2018) on their study, continuous reading improves students' vocabulary as well as their grasp of topics, both of which are important for comprehension and academic success (Duru&Koklu, 2011). According to Robinson and Weintraub (1973), students who have positive attitudes toward reading are more likely to seek out reading opportunities, be more motivated, and feel better about themselves. Positive attitudes can also encourage students to read more frequently and with greater success, which increases their reading achievement. Thus, positive attitude towards reading is a good head start to make learner a reader.

Meanwhile, despite this positive outlook of the pupils towards reading, they are still undecided as to their enjoyment in reading difficult texts. Their attitudes towards reading difficult text was affected with several factors such as their background knowledge, vocabulary and fluency, active reading skills, and critical thinking skills. Most of the studies anchored to the relation of vocabulary skills in difficulty of reading text. According to the University of Central Florida, this low performance in reading and their attitudes towards it are affected by several factors such as poor concentration, underdeveloped vocabulary, poor reading techniques, never developed a system for reading textbook, and blank mind syndrome. This statement is also supported with the study of Spear-Swerling that shows the three common patterns of poor reading: specific word-reading difficulties, specific reading-comprehension difficulties, and mixed reading difficulties. According to Romatillah (2014), the intricacy of word knowledge, as well as the restricted understanding of words, are some aspects making it difficult to learn vocabulary. In addition, Lee (2017) and Francie (2017) identified vocabulary as of the most important skills to be taught for the development of reading skills.

C. Reading Profile in Terms of Reading and Self- Efficacy

Table 3: Reading profile in terms of reading and self- efficacy

Item	Weighted Mean	Description
READING AND SELF-EFFICACY		
1. I think I read well and with understanding.	4.09	Agree
2. I read slowly so I have problems with understanding.	2.94	Undecided
3. I have difficulty in completing the reading assignments given to me.	3.05	Undecided
4. I read slowly so it makes me tired and bored.	2.69	Undecided
5. I have difficulty in understanding words (50% or more) in my reading assignments.	2.97	Undecided
6. I have to translate what I read into my home language before I really understand.	3.26	Undecided
7. I have difficulty in understanding the texts I have to read, especially the vocabulary.	3.32	Undecided
8. I have difficulty in extracting the main points in what I read.	3.37	Undecided
9. When I read I am always able to share and explain what I understood with friends and classmates.	3.69	Agree
10. I always find it difficult to answer questions based on readings assigned by lecturers and tutors.	3.29	Undecided
11. I always need help from friends, lecturers or tutors for me to understand the main ideas after reading academic texts.	4.00	Agree
12. I always try to understand the questions before answering.	4.36	Strongly Agree
13. I am a fast, highly skilled reader and I do not have problems understanding what I read.	2.59	Disagree
14. Academic reading takes up most of my time.	3.24	Undecided
Average Weighted Mean	3.35	Undecided

Another reason why learners do not enjoy reading difficult texts were the number of causal and referential connection, the explicitness of goals and topic familiarity (Liederholm, et. al. (2000). In connection to the vocabulary as a factor, neglecting the teaching of vocabulary in reading might affect students' academic performance. According to Nurjanah (2018), learners struggle with vocabulary or mastery, which is also associated with reading habits and the lack of engaging reading comprehension lessons they are given in class. In addition, Connor et al. (2002) mentioned that struggling readers in the intermediate grades improved less quickly when they read difficult texts than at more instructional levels. Furthermore, the lack of reading experience in children who are poor readers is aggravated by the fact that when these youngsters do read, they frequently find themselves reading far too challenging content. Going back to the role of the teachers, it is necessary to find the just right level of reading materials to the children. As stated by Compton et al. (2004) discovered that a text-leveling method can be made use of to select materials that are cognitively suited to children with low reading skills. The objective is that such a leveling system will be utilized to raise the possibility of successful and reinforcing reading experiences, increasing the likelihood that children who are having difficulty in their efforts to read may want to practice reading. Furthermore, La Berge and Samuels (1974) proposed that reading a variety of texts should help to improve the link between printed letters and words and their phonological representations. Individual letters, letter patterns, rimes, or morphemes may benefit from this enhancement. O'Connor et al. (2010) anticipated that students reading more challenging texts would make better decoding progress and have more opportunities to encounter unfamiliar vocabulary or partially understood terms in clarifying circumstances.

With regard to the category reading and self-efficacy of the respondents, “I always try to understand the questions before answering” with 4.36 weighted mean was the only factor were the respondents strongly agreed. Also, it was remarkably revealed that most of the respondents disagree on the factor “I am a fast, highly skilled reader and I do not have problems in understanding what I read” with 2.59 weighted mean.

Along reading and self-efficacy of the respondents, the data revealed that pupils of Mandaon North District elementary schools used their reading comprehension skills before answering a particular question. It can be inferred that based from the response of the pupils, reading comprehension was used in understanding the question. As mentioned by Olatunji (2011), comprehension and summary skills are highly essential to the success of a student for academic as well all-round exploits. Having this kind of practice, pupils can also improve their other linguistic skills (Iqbal, et.al. 2015).

On the other hand, the pupil-respondents disagree on the item “I am a fast, highly skilled reader and I do not have problems in understanding what I read” with 2.59 weighted mean.” In relation to self-efficacy of Bandura, the data

implied that most of them believed they can read but not as fast nor highly skilled. This data can be associated to the lack of self-esteem or lack of self-confidence among pupils. In reading, self-efficacy refers to the belief in one’s ability to read successfully (Boakye, 2015). According to studies, when struggling readers lack the drive to read, their chances of learning diminish considerably (Baker, Dreher and Guthrie, 2000). It also indicates how effective someone believes they will be in completing a task. Individuals who have a strong sense of self-efficacy in reading or who believe they are competent at reading are more likely to have happy reading experiences (Bessing G. 2017). Students who feel good about themselves are more likely to become better achievers. If they have a positive outlook and confidence their ability to learn increases. According to the Child Development Institute, LLC, “Self-esteem is a major key to success in life’. Students’ mindsets are shaped through success and failed experiences (Maatta, Mykkanen, & Jarvela, 2016). Giving children successful experiences with literacy in order to increase their confidence and self-concept as readers. When children believe they will achieve, they become more motivated, engaged and confident in their abilities, which aids in the formation of a positive self-concept as readers (Bessing, 2017).

D. Reading Profile in Terms of Reading Strategies

Table 4: Reading profile in terms of reading strategies

Item	Weighted Mean	Description
READING STRATEGIES		
1. Before I read a textbook, I look at its contents page and skim through it looking at headings and illustrations.	3.54	Agree
2. The first thing I do when I come across an unknown word is to look up the meaning.	3.68	Agree
3. I record new words and try to memorize them with their meanings.	3.30	Undecided
4. I ignore diagrams, maps, graphs, charts, which I come across in the course of my reading.	2.96	Undecided
5. I always take notes when I am reading.	3.40	Undecided
6. I always underline or highlights parts that I think are important when I am reading.	3.69	Agree
7. I always draw my own mind maps or flowcharts of the information about which I’m reading.	3.20	Undecided
8. I try to relate what I read to my own ideas and previous knowledge.	3.21	Undecided
9. I use questions like why, what and how to help me understand my reading better.	3.64	Agree
10. I always re-read sections when I do not understand what I am reading.	4.15	Agree
11. I form visual images when I read.	3.94	Agree
12. I summarize the main ideas in my head as I read.	3.58	Agree
13. The tutorials helped me understand difficult concepts.	4.03	Agree
14. The tutorials helped me understand the assigned readings better.	4.20	Agree
15. The mind maps helped me to identify the main points and supporting details.	3.26	Undecided
Average Weighted Mean	3.59	Agree

With reference to the category reading strategies, most of the respondents agreed on the factors “The tutorials helped me understand the assigned readings better” with 4.20 weighted mean. “I ignore diagrams, maps, graphs, charts which I come across in the course of my reading” with 2.96 weighted mean.

From the data gathered on the reading strategies of the respondents, the result shows that most of the pupils were using tutorials as their aid to better understand their reading assignments and or tasks. Accordingly, they can easily understand difficult concepts with the help of tutorials. According to the National Academies Press (1998), extra time spent in learning will assist youngsters in achieving reading levels that will allow them to be productive through their years in school and beyond. In this regard, pupils who were instructed by their classmates or by older students outperformed untutored individuals (Cohen et al., 1982; Mathes & Fuchs, 1994). Similarly, on the study conducted by the Department of Education in Washington DC, tutoring may additionally improve self-confidence in reading, drive to read, and behavior in tutees as well as peers or cross-age tutors. The data can be linked to the scaffolding of Vygotsky which stated that with the help of more knowledgeable others the learner can gain more increased knowledge and the like compared to doing it alone. As to Al Eissa & Al-Bargi (2017), students showed a positive attitude to the scaffolding technique as a motivational factor to their learning. The inclusion of this technique is a great help to teachers to aid pupil in reading especially those difficult texts. During the reading process, readers rely on contextual information encompassing syntactic, semantic, and discourse limitations that influence their perception of the text (Rivers, 1988; Salem, 2017). As a result, pupils require instructor aid, or instructional scaffolding, to understand and comprehend the message behind the reading activities (Salem, 2017). Readers gain a larger perspective on reading materials through scaffolding processes, which improves comprehension (Clark & Graves, 2004). Instructional scaffolding are also important in aiding reading and ensuring autonomous comprehension or understanding (Many, 2002; Mayer, 1993). As a result, comprehension is required

because reading "cannot be called without comprehending" (Karasakaloglu, 2010, p. 222). Scaffolds that are well-built maximize student learning, produce a supportive environment, and encourage autonomy among learners.

The data also revealed that the item “I ignore diagrams, maps, graphs, charts which I come across in the course of my reading” got a 2.96 weighted mean which was categorized as undecided. Accordingly, Dreyfus & Eisenberg (1990) stated that Reading a diagram is an acquired skill that should not be left to chance. As stated by Glazer (2011), a common cognitive error in graph reading is understanding data iconically, which means 'viewing the graph as a picture'. This happens when students perceive graphs as literal representations of circumstances rather than abstract numeric information (Janvier, 1998; Leinhardt, Zaslavsky, & Stein, 1990; McDermott, Rosenquist, & van Zee, 1987). Other common difficulties include confusion between the slope and the height (Janvier, 1998), confusion between an interval and a point, viewing a graph as a collection of discrete points (Kerslake, 1981), focusing on x-y trends (Shah, Mayer, & Hegarty, 1999), and difficulties caused by the amount of information presented in the graph, its format, and inappropriate choice of visual features (Brockmann, 1991; Shah, Freedman, & Vekiri, 2005; Tufte, 1986) or teachers' expertise (Bowen & Roth, 2005).

Graph interpretation is an essential skill that all students must have in order to make sense of and transmit information presented in graphs, which are prevalent in society (e.g., magazines, newspapers, television, and websites). According to the NCTM (2000), children in early school should be able to read off the data, seek out specific details offered in the data, recognize quantities, and compare two single data points. Older elementary pupils should be able to see the big picture and identify it. Students in middle school should do more, allowing them to detect trends in data, and by high school, they should be able to make conclusions from graphs (Glazer, 2011). In teaching, teachers must introduce graphics in the reading activity and as much as possible, they should teach or guide the learner in reading and analyzing a certain graphics.

E. Reading Profile in Terms of Reading Habits

Table 5: Reading profile in terms of reading habits

Item	Weighted Mean	Description
READING HABITS		
I read for pleasure.	3.74	Agree
I read magazines and or newspapers every week.	2.62	Undecided
I often go to the library to look for information related to my courses.	2.88	Undecided
I always read my lecture notes and prescribed materials.	4.10	Agree
I only read academic articles and prescribed texts when I have an assignment.	3.60	Agree
I have designed a study timetable for my personal study.	3.00	Undecided
I strictly follow my study timetable.	2.91	Undecided
Average Weighted Mean	3.26	Undecided

On the reading habits of the respondents, most of them agreed with the factors “I always read my lecture notes and prescribed materials” with 4.10. weighted mean and undecided on the item “I read magazines and or newspapers every week” with 2.62 weighted mean.

As mentioned by Rabia, et. al. (2017) on their study, they claimed that habits play an important role in the formation of knowledge and perceptual abilities. Study habits reveal how much a person intends to study, how far he wishes to progress, and how much he wishes to earn. In addition, it was discovered in their study that there is a considerable association between students' study habits and academic success. As to Solis (2013) reading frequency is also deemed to have a significant relationship with the English proficiency of the respondents from the data collected. This means that the longer the time is spent on reading, the more proficient an individual becomes in English. Moreover, on the study of Mashayekhi, et. al. (2014) they revealed that study habits are undoubtedly one of the elements that influence academic achievements; individuals with higher study skills have more active learning and are more immersed in educational subjects, and so have better memorizing and remembering abilities. They also cited in the study of Sirohi that poor study habits were identified as one of the leading factors of students' poor academic achievement.

Along with the respondents' reading habits, most of them reviewed and reread their prescribed reading materials and lecture notes. Also, most of them are reading for pleasure. According to the study of Whitten, Labby and Sullivan (2019), students who read self-selected literature for pleasure would experience greater academic success than their non-reading peers. According to Bahrami and Nosratzadeh (2017) reviewing the note, which amplifies thoughts, is a vital step to improving comprehension. According to Kobayashi (2005), taking notes is a crucial tool for improved comprehension. Roy et al. (2014) claimed that note-taking effectively improves the capacity of readers

to take notes, help them recall some details, and also improve their listening proficiency, making it advantageous to employ in language learning classrooms. Marzano, Pickering, & Pollock (2001) indicating that effective summarizing and taking notes result in increased student learning. Helping kids grasp how information is arranged will allow them to better synthesize what they read or hear. Students who are able to concisely learn to synthesize information, a higher-order thinking skill that includes analyzing information, identifying key concepts, and defining extraneous information, and it also improves students' reading skills and precisely are useful to make progress in their lessons' reading tasks (O'Malley & Chamot, 1990; Carrel, 1998; Taraban, 2004; Phakiti, 2006; Motallebzadeh & Mamdoodi, 2011).

Contrarily, most of the respondents were undecided on reading newspapers and magazines every week because of the absence or unavailability of the said reading materials. The result is also associated to difficulty of the reading materials which is related to the use of vocabulary. Newspaper and magazines are considered as authentic reading materials so the inclusion of these can benefit mostly the students. Rao (2019) discussed comprehensively the role of newspaper and magazine in his study and these are follows: improve language skills, increase motivation and develop critical thinking skills. In addition, as valuable as general information is, it improves students' reading and writing skills, broadens their knowledge base, and strengthens their academic performance. (Miracle, 2013). Furthermore, Rao (2019) also indicated that the teacher must planned carefully on how to make those reading materials to suit to learners' needs. Thus, teachers should strategize the use of this supplemental readings to expose children to different reading materials. Moreover, teacher can make use of the supplemental reading materials as a prescribed learning or reading tool for them to be familiar with those kind of reading materials.

IV. PUPILS' COGNITIVE AND AFFECTIVE READING PROFILES IN RELATION TO AGE, SEX, AND FAMILY ECONOMIC STATUS

A. Relationship Between Cognitive and Affective Reading Profile and Age

Table 6: Relationship between cognitive and affective reading profile and age

Background Factors	Computed x ²	df	α	Tabulated Value	Remarks
Past Experiences with Reading	20.002	16	0.05	26.296	No significant relationship
Attitude Towards Reading	6.690	16	0.05	26.296	No significant relationship
Reading and Self-Efficacy	11.421	16	0.05	26.296	No significant relationship
Reading Strategies	9.165	16	0.05	26.296	No significant relationship
Reading Habits	9.325	16	0.05	26.296	No significant relationship

Based on Table 6, it was found out that age does not have any significant relationship to cognitive and affective reading profiles. This finding has ample support in the literature. In the study of Voyles (2011), as related to reading, she believed that pupil age did not matter. A statistical investigation of the link between student age and student academic success in the reading domain revealed that there was no relationship. Due to limited studies that

focused on the significant relation of age to reading, the researcher linked the results to the relation of age to academic success for children in the elementary grades. Some research (Demeis & Stearns, 1992; Dietz & Wilson, 1985) reported no significant association between age and achievement, whilst others (Dietz & Wilson, 1985; Gredler, 1980) revealed no age influence on first graders' academic performance. Wood, Powell, and Knight (1984) concurred,

but added that "...chronological age of children entering kindergarten within the range of 4 to 6 years is unrelated to eventual success or failure". In addition to this, Imlack, A., et.al. (2017) in their study, age, IQ, gender, working memory, psychosocial factors, and common brain gene polymorphisms connected to brain function, plasticity, and degeneration were found to have no effect on academic achievement. These findings show that aging does not hinder academic accomplishment and that distinct cognitive skills, as well as lifetime participation in cognitively

stimulating activities, can increase academic success in older individuals.

Most of the studies was able to link significant relationship of age to reading background, wherein most claims identified age as a factor that affect reading and academic achievement as well. To note, the data presented above was treated as age as whole and not by each category of age.

B. Relationship Between Cognitive and Affective Reading Profile and Sex

Table 7: Relationship between cognitive and affective reading profile and sex

Background Factors	Computed χ^2	df	α	Tabulated Value	Remarks
Past Experiences with Reading	7.395	4	0.05	9.488	No significant relationship
Attitude Towards Reading	5.145	4	0.05	9.488	No significant relationship
Reading and Self-Efficacy	6.755	4	0.05	9.488	No significant relationship
Reading Strategies	2.845	4	0.05	9.488	No significant relationship
Reading Habits	2.788	4	0.05	9.488	No significant relationship

Based on the data above, sex does not have a relationship to reading background factors. Relating this finding to related literature, Pagal, et. al. (2017) and PIRLS (2006) research data showed with the exception of Spain and Luxembourg, girls outperformed boys in reading achievement. The gender gap in these two countries was not considerable (Mullis et al., 2007). This demonstrates that in the current study, female students do not always thrive at all levels of reading comprehension. Males outperformed females in terms of literal performance. In terms of gender, there is no better reader; male and female readers have different reading attitudes and behaviors that help them absorb and comprehend reading texts. As a result, both genders have been found to be no better readers at these two levels. It was also noted in the study of Oda (2018) gender has an effect on reading comprehension at the college level, but it is not statistically significant (except for the critical level). A study on the association between gender and reading comprehension in general cannot generalize the finding that one gender is better than the other. Any study undertaken on such a link appears to be influenced by several side factors. Whether the source of such factors is

the socio-cultural context or the context of the study itself, or a factor represented by the nature of the reading comprehension test passage, nature of the test questions, or any other linguistic or non-linguistic factor, they could play a role in the study itself. Also, Barron, et. al. (2006) claimed that modest changes in their data did not result in significant benefits for girls in terms of literacy ability at these early levels. Instead, the type of school was found to be a considerably more significant predictor of both literacy achievement and attitudes toward literacy. Willoughby (2010) found that boys and girls have similar reading inclinations, but this varies by person, not gender. This suggests that students require opportunity to select literature based on their own likes and interests rather than gender. Voyles (2011) stated on her study that there was no relationship between student gender and academic success in reading. As to Tor-Akwer, et.al (2014) there is no significant joint effect of independent variables of (gender, age, marital status, level of study and occupation) on reading habits of students. Vlachos & Papadimitriou (2015), gender was discovered to play no significant influence on reading performance.

C. Relationship Between Cognitive and Affective Reading Profile and Family Economic Status

Table 8: Relationship between cognitive and affective reading profile and family economic status

Background Factors	Computed χ^2	df	α	Tabulated Value	Remarks
Past Experiences with Reading	38.266	16	0.05	26.296	With Significant Relationship
Attitude Towards Reading	28.296	16	0.05	26.296	With Significant Relationship
Reading and Self-Efficacy	33.479	16	0.05	26.296	With Significant Relationship
Reading Strategies	47.953	16	0.05	26.296	With Significant Relationship
Reading Habits	78.979	16	0.05	26.296	With Significant Relationship

The data revealed that family economic status has a relationship to the cognitive and affective reading profile. Most claims supported that academic achievements are closely linked to family economic status. Chen, Kong, Gso& Mo (2018) found out that the higher the degree of education, occupational status, and income of the parents, the higher the children's reading ability, and vice versa. In terms of income, low-income households may be unable to provide

required living commodities such as a home, a study place, or a computer, as well as other supplements such as extracurricular books, newspapers, and magazines for children. Also as to Thomson, De Bortoli& Underwood (2017), students from low-income families face a disadvantage in school because they lack an academic home environment, which effects their academic progress. Books in the home, in particular, have been found over many years

in many large-scale worldwide studies to be one of the most influential determinants on student accomplishment. Furthermore, Hemmerechts, Agirdag&Kavadias (2016), found that children from higher-income families are more likely to have good attitudes toward reading. From the study of Le, Thi-Thu-Hien, et. al. (2019), they looked into the relationship between students' household socioeconomic level and book supply sources. Regardless of reading desire, kids from affluent homes were more likely to purchase and receive books as gifts than students from lower-income families. They determined that students growing up in wealthy homes are more financially supported and typically do not have to spend time doing chores or helping their parents earn revenue, allowing them to devote more time to schoolwork and reading.

On the other side, some researches claimed that SES or family income does not significantly affect the achievement of the children but it was the parent involvement to their children's learning. It was suggested that parents should devote more time to family education. Parents' education, career, and income cannot be changed quickly, but education attitudes and parent-child connections are rather straightforward to modify. Parents should encourage and aid their children's academic lives by creating a better family environment.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher drew the following conclusions; (1) the low weighted mean obtained on the factor; reading and self-efficacy and reading habits can be a contributing factors on the low reading proficiency level of the pupils; (2) past experiences with reading, attitudes towards reading and reading strategies are also a great contributor to the reading experiences of the pupil; (3) age and gender do not have a significant relation to reading but they may still be factors on what appropriate tasks to be given along reading activity, and (4) family income is related to the cognitive and affective reading profiles of the child and together may be explored further as to the effect on the reading achievement of pupils.

In view of the findings and conclusions generated by this study, the following recommendations are given. Interventions may be given based on the family economic status of pupils, in conjunction with other proven factors in the literature. Specific intervention programs may be given based on the data. Teachers must address the reading issues of the pupils as early as possible by providing the right reading intervention based on individual needs and devise an activity matrix along with the pupils' reading proficiency progress. In the absence of library services, teachers must provide a mini-library in their classrooms equipped with books of different genres and levels and other supplemental readings. Inclusion of library time within the class program is also recommended. Parents should also take their active role in developing the study habits of their children. For future researchers, conduct a study that will identify other background factors that influence the reading profile of the pupils such as teachers' factor and have focus on one or two reading background factors.

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